

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION AND ITS IMPACT ON THE STRUCTURE AND EFFICIENCY OF MODERN BUSINESS

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Abstract

The article examines the impact of digital transformation (DT) on modern business. It analyzes its effects on organizational structures, business processes, and customer interactions. Key aspects such as the implementation of artificial intelligence technologies, big data, and automation, as well as the socio-economic and cultural factors determining the success of DT, are considered. The study emphasizes the importance of adapting business models to new conditions, including changes in corporate culture and professional training. The article provides examples of successful DT implementations and discusses the challenges companies face. It concludes by highlighting the strategic importance of DT in enhancing business efficiency and competitiveness.

Keywords: digital transformation (DT), artificial intelligence (AI), big data, automation, corporate culture, business models, business efficiency.

Introduction

Digital transformation (DT) occupies a central role in the development of the modern economy. It establishes new rules of competition, reshapes business processes, and defines the trajectories of global economic growth. The application of digital technologies enables companies to adapt to rapidly changing conditions, optimize costs, and increase productivity. This makes the study of the impact of DT on business highly relevant.

In recent years, digital technologies have penetrated almost all areas of business. The use of artificial intelligence (AI), big data, and automation has become an integral part of the strategies of leading global companies. However, not all organizations are capable of effectively adapting to these changes. Successful transition to a digital model requires consideration of numerous factors, including socio-economic, cultural, and technological characteristics.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the impact of DT on business structure and efficiency. The study employs methods of systemic analysis and case study examination. Particular attention is paid to changes in organizational models, improvements in production processes, and the transformation of customer experience.

Main part. The concept of DT

The process of integrating digital technologies into a company's strategy, structure, and operational activities is known as DT. It is not merely the adoption of technologies but a fundamental change in how businesses operate and interact with their environment. The term came into widespread use in the early 21st century when technological innovations began reshaping traditional approaches to business [1].

Initially, DT was understood as the automation of routine operations. However, with the advancement of technologies, its meaning has expanded. Today, the concept encompasses business process optimization, the adoption of customer-oriented strategies, and the use of analytics for decision-making. It also involves the transition to flexible organizations capable of quickly adapting to market changes. According to Statista, global spending on DT will reach \$2,5 trillion in 2024 and \$3,9 trillion by 2027. As of 2023, the United States was considered the world's most digitally competitive country [2].

Several fundamental elements form the basis of DT. Among them, technologies play a pivotal role, enabling automation and data analytics [3]. Processes hold a significant place as they are optimized for greater efficiency and transparency. Organizational culture acts as a catalyst for change, fostering the adoption of innovations. Company structures also undergo transformation, becoming more flexible and collaboration-oriented (fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Components of DT

A systematic approach is essential for DT. The integration of technologies, adaptation of processes, and development of culture enable companies to transform successfully. This makes it not only a technological phenomenon but also a social one, impacting the entire business ecosystem.

The impact of DT on business structures

Traditional hierarchical structures with rigid lines of authority and highly centralized management are rapidly giving place to more flexible, adaptive forms thanks to DT. The objective need for rapid responses to changes in the market environment, optimization of internal processes, and enhancement of the innovative potential drives this change. Adaptive structures include cross-functional teams, horizontal connections, and decentralized decision-making. The ability to execute tasks more quickly strengthens interdepartmental collaboration.

As digital technologies become more significant, new roles and professions emerge, playing a central role in the successful transformation of companies. Data specialists, big data analysts, AI developers, and cybersecurity experts are becoming indispensable members of business teams [4]. These professionals ensure the implementation, support, and development of technologies, contributing to the creation of innovative products and optimization of processes. Such changes, in turn, require a reevaluation of approaches to employee training and professional development. Companies are investing in upskilling programs and engaging external experts to educate their staff.

Successful examples of DT can be seen in global companies like Amazon and Alibaba. **Amazon** has implemented a model focused on data analytics and automation. According to company reports, in 2023, Amazon invested approximately \$75,9 billion in information and communication technologies, including AI, big data, robotics, and the Internet of Things. These investments accelerated operational processes, introduced personalized recommendations, and improved supply chain management.

Similarly, **Alibaba** integrated AI and blockchain technologies to enhance its electronic platforms. The company launched Tongyi Qianwen, a chatbot similar

to ChatGPT, supporting both English and Chinese languages. It has been incorporated into various business operations, including the DingTalk messaging app and the Tmall Genie voice assistant. These initiatives enabled Alibaba to create an ecosystem that spans retail, logistics, and financial services, significantly improving efficiency and expanding market reach.

Kazakhstani companies are also actively adopting digital technologies to enhance efficiency and competitiveness on the global stage. According to the Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the level of digitalization in the country continues to grow annually. In the first half of 2024, 918 5G base stations were installed across 20 cities, providing stable and high-speed internet connectivity. The total number of public services, including business-related ones, provided electronically has reached 93,3% [5].

One notable example of successful DT is the company **Kazakhtelecom**. It launched the «Smart City» platform aimed at improving the quality of life in Kazakhstan's cities through the implementation of intelligent systems for managing transportation, energy supply, and safety. This initiative reduced energy consumption costs and response times for emergency services, demonstrating the effectiveness of digital solutions in the real economy.

The changes brought about by DT require not only technical solutions but also cultural shifts. Successful examples show that companies capable of adapting to new realities gain a competitive advantage. They demonstrate that flexibility, the development of new skills, and a strategic approach to change are the key drivers of transformation. As a result, companies become more resilient to external challenges and better prepared for innovative growth.

Enhancing business efficiency through digitalization

Modern companies actively utilize digital technologies to automate processes, integrate data, and improve customer interactions. These measures not only optimize costs but also enhance the quality of services provided, which is particularly crucial for maintaining competitive positions (table 1).

Table 1

Features of enhancing business efficiency through digitalization [6]

Area of digitalization	Results	Practical example
Process automation	Increased productivity, cost reduction, and elimination of human errors.	Use of robots in warehouses to speed up order processing.
Data integration	Improved analytics, enhanced accuracy and speed of decision-making.	Implementation of corporate ERP systems to optimize supply chain management.
Customer experience improvement	Increased customer satisfaction, simplified interaction through new service introductions.	Use of personalized offers and multichannel approaches in retail.
Logistics	Optimization of routes, improved reliability, and reduced delivery times.	Use of monitoring and transport management technologies to optimize logistics.
Finance	Faster transactions, fewer errors in processing.	Application of blockchain solutions to increase transparency and security of operations.
Marketing	Enhanced effectiveness of advertising campaigns, increased audience engagement.	Use of AI to analyze preferences and ensure precise targeting.

Digitalization has become the foundation of strategic transformations for businesses, enabling companies to adapt to modern challenges. It helps create more sustainable business models by integrating technologies into key aspects of management and operational activities. These changes contribute to the development of new approaches to organizing work, making processes more flexible and reliable.

It is important to note that digitalization is not limited to automation or the adoption of technologies. It is a process that impacts organizational culture, management approaches, and customer interactions. Companies that implement digital innovations gain the ability not only to enhance productivity but also to access new markets, creating competitive advantages.

Furthermore, digitalization fosters collaboration within organizations and between partners. This allows businesses to build ecosystems where the integration of data and technologies generates new value for all participants. Such approaches are becoming especially relevant in the context of globalization and the growing importance of networked interaction.

Socio-economic aspects of DT

The socio-economic and cultural structures of society are profoundly impacted by DT. It reshapes the labor market by creating new professions while eliminating outdated ones, exacerbates the digital divide between regions and countries, and highlights the importance of corporate culture and leadership in successfully adapting to new conditions [7].

Digitalization continues to shape the labor market, generating new jobs in technology-related fields while

simultaneously reducing the demand for traditional professions. According to a study by the World Economic Forum, by 2025, approximately 97 million new roles related to AI, data processing, and digital marketing are expected to emerge, while 85 million jobs may be displaced by automation. This underscores the need for workforce retraining and upskilling to meet the demands of these new professions.

The digital divide between regions and countries remains a significant issue. According to the International Telecommunication Union, in 2023, approximately 2,9 billion people still lacked internet access, with the majority residing in developing countries. This limits their opportunities for education, employment, and access to information, exacerbating socio-economic inequality.

Successful DT requires not only the implementation of technologies but also changes in corporate culture and leadership. Companies that encourage innovation, flexibility, and continuous learning adapt more effectively to digital changes.

Barriers and challenges of DT

Significant opportunities are offered by DT for companies, but its implementation comes with numerous challenges. These challenges affect both technical and organizational aspects, creating obstacles to the successful realization of changes. Limited resources, cybersecurity issues, and internal resistance within companies can slow down or completely block the transformation process. Understanding these barriers is essential for developing effective strategies to overcome them (table 2).

Table 2

Key barriers to DT [8]

Barrier category	Problem description	Potential consequences
Financial constraints	Lack of funds for developing and implementing digital solutions.	Delays in project execution; selection of outdated or incomplete technologies.
Technological constraints	Limited availability of modern technologies; insufficient employee skills.	Reduced digitalization efficiency; absence of long-term technological progress.
Cybersecurity	Risk of data breaches; insufficient system protection.	Loss of financial and reputational resources; reduced customer trust.
Resistance to change	Employees' and managers' reluctance to adapt to new processes.	Slower technology implementation; increased costs of change.
Lack of strategy	Absence of clear digitalization goals and pathways to achieve them.	Chaotic technology adoption; low return on investment.

Barriers to DT arise from a combination of internal and external factors, which require a comprehensive approach to overcome. Companies face the challenge of balancing innovation with ongoing operational tasks. This makes the process of implementing changes more complex than it might initially appear.

For a successful transformation, organizations need to focus on a long-term strategy rather than just addressing short-term problems. Careful planning and consistent implementation of changes help minimize risks associated with resource shortages or employee unpreparedness. Additionally, overcoming barriers often requires the involvement of external experts and the creation of cross-functional teams. Special attention should be given to fostering a culture that supports change. This is not just a matter of employee motivation but also their engagement in the process. The

clearer the goals of transformation, the less resistance it generates.

Ultimately, overcoming the barriers of digitalization requires the integration of organizational efforts, technological solutions, and strategic leadership. These measures provide the foundation for long-term success and sustainable business development in the digital age.

Conclusion

The structure and efficiency of modern businesses are comprehensively impacted by DT, which serves as a driver of strategic change. It helps companies make adaptations to fast-changing market conditions with the integration of technologies, automation, and enhancement of customer interactions. These changes raise productivity and also enable businesses to devise more sustainable models with a focus on innovation and flexibility. A digital model transition requires an organized

approach in terms of technology implementation, corporate culture development, and organizational structural reevaluation.

However, DT comes with numerous challenges, including financial constraints, technological barriers, cybersecurity issues, and internal resistance to change. To surmount these challenges, long-term planning is necessary, as well as involvement from outside experts and the setup of cross-functional teams. Companies that successfully applied digital innovations and adapted to new conditions gained a competitive edge, strengthened their market positions, and assured themselves of sustainable growth in the global economy.

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